

1 **EGR1 activation during VEGF-A inhibition with bevacizumab.**

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6 We measured total transcription in human cancer cells by RNA-sequencing following *in vitro* treatment
7 with bevacizumab to determine without bias genes most affected VEGF-A blockade in the transcriptome.
8 We report here the discovery of *EGR1* as a feedback response gene mediating compensatory signaling in
9 response to bevacizumab (Avastin) growth factor restriction.

10 Citations

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